

Case Studies

Ocean currents connect life throughout the oceans. This means we can't look at one area on its own and have to think about how changes in other places might impact on it.

However, the scale of the ocean means that we need to focus on a few areas to gather information from. These are the ATLAS Case Studies. They have been carefully chosen to cover a wide range of deep-sea environments as well as connections via the major Atlantic currents.

Some of the areas include 'Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems' (VMEs): groups of creatures, communities or habitats that may be vulnerable to impacts from fishing activities.

Map of Atlantic Ocean with Currents

ATLAS Case Study Locations

- ★ 1 LoVe Observatory
- ★ 2 Faroe Shetland Channel
- ★ 3 Rockall Bank, northern Northeast Atlantic
- ★ 4 Mingulay Reef
- ★ 5 Porcupine Seabight (Southwest of Ireland)
- ★ 6 Bay of Biscay
- ★ 7 Gulf of Cádiz/ Strait of Gibraltar/ Alborán Sea
- ★ 8 Azores
- ★ 9 Reykjanes Ridge
- ★ 10 Davis Strait, Eastern Arctic
- ★ 11 Flemish Cap
- ★ 12 Mid-Atlantic Canyons

Project Partners

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| 1 The University of Edinburgh | 12 Dynamic Earth |
| 2 Aarhus Universitet | 13 University of Oxford |
| 3 IMAR – Instituto do Mar | 14 University College Dublin |
| 4 Secretária Regional Do Mar, Ciência e Tecnologia | 15 University College London |
| 5 British Geological Survey | 16 National University of Ireland, Galway |
| 6 Gianni Consultancy | 17 University of Liverpool |
| 7 Intsitut Francais de Recherche pour L'Exploitation de la Mer | 18 University of Southern Denmark |
| 8 Marine Scotland | 19 The Arctic University of Norway |
| 9 Universitaet Bremen | 20 Scottish Association for Marine Science |
| 10 Iodine | 21 Seascope Consultants |
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